

EXTRA-CURRICULUM INDEPENDENT WORK AND ITS ROLE OF LEARNING ACTIVITIES OF LANGUAGE STUDENTS

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***Abstract:** A systematic approach to the organization and management of independent work of students at the university is considered. The importance of independent work of students in the educational activity of students as a condition and way of intensifying their cognitive activity is substantiated. Pedagogical conditions are proposed that contribute to the effective organization and management of independent work of students at the university and the implementation of an individually differentiated approach to teaching students in higher education. Independent work of students is considered as a special type of educational activity, in the structure of which one can single out motivational, goal-setting, performance and control components.*

***Key words:** independent work, systematic approach, cognitive activity, general intellectual skills, motivation, pedagogical conditions, logical and content side.*

Extracurricular independent work of students of the faculty of languages is one of the types of their independent work on mastering a foreign language, which involves a differentiated approach to students and individualization of learning. Teaching a foreign language in a group of 15-20 people encounters significant difficulties due to the difference in the individual psychological characteristics of students. The same material, the same teaching methods, the same rhythm of work are simultaneously offered to students endowed with different abilities, memory, attention, type of thinking and perception, temperament, emotions, and the like. In the context of a radical restructuring of the system of vocational education and the transition from knowledge-centered education, based on the transfer of knowledge,

skills, to personality-oriented, humanistic education, the purpose of which is to recognize human individuality and develop the intellectual, emotional, spiritual and moral potential of the individual, independent work of students is becoming one of the most important problems in the organization of training.

Extracurricular independent work of students as a form of mastering foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities has the following advantages:

1) In extracurricular independent work, the conditions necessary for mastering a foreign language are personified. The student himself determines the pace of work, the ways of its implementation, based on personal qualities;

2) Differences in the individual psychological characteristics of students predetermine different learning technologies. For mastering a foreign language, such mental processes as thinking (type of thinking), perception, memory are of particular importance;

3) Extracurricular independent work on the language contributes to the formation of positive personality traits: independence, initiative, purposefulness, systematic and thorough work, and so on. Students experience satisfaction from their own "inquiry", learn to rationally use their time, cultivate conscious discipline and volitional self-control, develop memory, thinking, and the ability to creative activity. The concept of independent work is multifaceted; therefore, it is quite natural that it has not received a single interpretation in the pedagogical and methodological literature. The essence and signs of independent work are revealed in different ways, various classifications of its types are given.

The term "independent work" is used by domestic methodologists in the meaning of the method of organization and implementation of educational and cognitive activities, as an integral and specific part of the learning process or a form of organization of the educational process, a type of educational activity, and also as a means of involving students in independent cognitive and practical activities. Some authors avoid using the term "independent work" and use only the term "independent activity", others consider the concept of independent activity as broader in relation to independent work, including self-organization, self-

management, self-control and independent work. Sometimes independent work is opposed to lesson forms of student work [1].

The issue related to independent work is comprehensively analyzed in the studies of P.I. Pikasisty, who considers it in the educational process both as a means of organizing and managing students' independent activities, and as a specific form of educational cognition [4]. With this approach to independent work, the interests of both subjects of the educational process are taken into account: for the teacher, independent work is an instrument of pedagogical guidance for the independent cognitive activity of students, and for students it is a type of cognitive activity associated with an independent solution of a learning problem. It is hard not to agree with P.I. Pikasy in defining the essence of independent learning activity, which does not mean that the student works without outside help. The main feature of independent activity as a didactic category is manifested in the fact that the goal of the student's activity simultaneously carries the function of managing this activity. Therefore, the subject content of each educational action is realized by the student and becomes the immediate goal of this action [2].

Most of the above definitions refer to independent work in general, regardless of the venue and the subject being studied. Our study considers extracurricular independent work in English by students of the Faculty of Languages.

Based on the objectives of the study and shifting the focus to the sphere of students' personalities, we tried to give a working definition of extracurricular independent work in a foreign language by students of the language faculty as a special form of learning activity, due to the individual psychological and personal characteristics of students and contributing to the formation of their individual learning style through mastering a wide range of cognitive strategies (rational methods and techniques used to learn a foreign language).

Thus, extracurricular independent work of students of the language faculty as a special, highest form of learning activity involves students' awareness of their abilities, goals, methods and techniques of learning a foreign language, as well as the development of cognitive independence.

It seems that independence should be considered in two different but interrelated aspects: as a characteristic of the student's activity in a particular learning situation and as a personality trait. The first, obviously, participates in the formation of the second. Independence as a characteristic of the student's activity in a particular learning situation is the ability to constantly demonstrate the ability to achieve the goal of the activity without outside help. At the same time, it must be emphasized that independence should be associated not only with the ability to act without outside help, but precisely with the ability to achieve the goal of the study without outside support. Absolute, complete independence is impossible in learning, so it should be assessed taking into account the extent to which the participation of the teacher is objectively necessary. It is this kind of cognitive independence that can be recognized as optimal.

External signs of the independence of the student are planning his activities, completing the task without the direct participation of the teacher, constant self-control over the progress and results of the work performed, and its subsequent correction. The inner side of cognitive independence is formed by the need-motivational sphere, the mental, moral-volitional efforts of the student, aimed at achieving the goal without outside help. The level of independence is not related to the time factor. Learning activity can be qualified as independent, regardless of how long it lasted.

In didactic and methodological literature, it is customary to distinguish three stages of independence that a student goes through in the process of forming this quality of educational knowledge: reproductive-imitative, search-performing, creative [3]. Independence begins with imitative actions at the stage of joint activity of the subjects of the educational process, passes through the stage of the emergence of awareness and arbitrariness of one's own mental processes, the stage of reproducing learned actions to the stage of creative activity [3]. It should be emphasized that in refraction to foreign language speech activity, the independence of students should be manifested primarily in the desire to independently use the language for the purpose of communication (the ability to express and justify one's

point of view, build a detailed monologue statement, and so on). The degree of independence of students can be different. It depends primarily on the individual speech experience of students, as well as on the degree of development of speech supports, for example: the more detailed the plan of the intended statement is, the less independent is the speech of students.

The objectives of this study correspond to the allocation of reproducing, transforming and creative types of independent work. Will all three types of independent work be inherent in 1st year students of the Faculty of Languages when mastering a foreign language as a means of communication? I think so.

The reproducing type of independent work is performed by the student during the initial acquaintance with the object being assimilated. It would be wrong to believe that successful learning of independence is achieved only in the process of independent actions of the student. In educational work, there are always actions according to a ready-made model, which are often imitative in nature, and the better the student masters the skills of actions according to the model, the more successfully his independence in educational and practical work is manifested [2].

When performing independent work according to the model, the independence of students is manifested in the replacement of some language means, the transformation of sentences, and in general, a foreign language statement is an act of reproducing the content and language form of the material read or listened to without any significant changes or with minimal changes in the language form of the sample. At the same time, students do not perform such actions as independent choice and combination of language units. Therefore, the degree of independence of students in the language design of the statement is not great. The abilities and skills of independent work of the reproducing type as a form of learning activity among 1st year students have already been formed in the conditions of the school course of learning a foreign language and require only some correction. We are talking about students striving for verbatim (full) reproduction of any language material, which prevents further formation of the ability to use the language independently for communicative purposes.

A higher level of independence is represented by independent work of a transformative type, characterized by a meaningful modification of the acquired information, the ability to explain the new through the already familiar, to independently comprehend the internal structure of the material being studied. In the course of performing independent work of a transforming type, landmarks and supports (plan, key words and expressions, logical-semantic schemes, and so on) assist students in preparing an utterance both in terms of presenting the content and in terms of choosing means of expression. When performing tasks on supports, students have a greater degree of independence, creativity, which is manifested in the ability to navigate the language material, highlight the main thing when drawing up a plan, answer questions, argue or refute, formulate conclusions. It seems to us that search and performance independence, which involves the actualization of such mental functions as analysis and synthesis, comparison, generalization, choice, combination and is associated with the adoption of an educational task and the search for ways to solve it, it is sufficiently formed among 1st year students of the Faculty of Languages. Therefore, independent work of a transformative type requires only some control action on the part of the teacher, which can be in the form of additional instructions and recommendations.

It is the development of students' creative independence in using the studied language as a means of communication that is the main goal of teaching at the Faculty of Languages. This becomes possible when performing independent work of a creative type, when students create statements of various communicative types, choose ways to solve a learning problem, determine the content of a foreign language statement themselves, choose and combine words, syntactic structures, express their judgments and personal attitude to what they are studying.

An essential sign of independent work of a creative type is the development of a complex transfer of learned methods of speech action to new non-identical conditions of activity, the ability to compose a complete orienting basis of action when performing a creative task, that is, “to highlight all the objective conditions

that determine its correct implementation” [3]. Creative tasks contain conditions that stimulate the emergence of problem situations that can be created in various ways:

- by posing the problem by the teacher;
- by posing a more or less defined problem, in the process of finding a solution to which the student independently discovers a new additional problem (foreseen when constructing a problem situation);
- by presenting such conditions, analyzing which the student himself must understand and formulate the problems contained in them. The most important condition for the successful organization of independent work of a creative type is the inclusion of students in the process of independent solution of subjectively new and significant problems for them [6].

Thus, extracurricular independent work of students of the language faculty as a special form of educational activity is the result of pedagogical interaction between the teacher and students in the process of learning a foreign language. Based on this, the teacher organizes and manages independent work on mastering foreign language speech activity in such a way that students have to show an increasing degree of cognitive independence when performing independent work of a reproducing, transforming creative type.

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